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Authors: G. Aiello

Contributors: J. Aktaa, O. Ancelet, M. E. Angiolini, G. Barbieri, M. Blat-Yrieix, S. Dubiez-Le Goff, G. Dundulis, L. Forest, G. M. Giannuzzi, A. Grybėnas, S. Holmström, C. Jia-Chao, T. Lebarbé, H-Y Lee, P. Matheron, K-F Nilsson, R. Pohja, C. Schroer, G. Smith, C. Testani, K. Zhang.

Approval: M. Utili

MATTER project

EC Scientific Officer: Mykola Džubinský

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Summary

This report constitutes the deliverable D4.8 – «Synthesis of the recommendations» of the Work Package 4 - «Design Rules» of the MATTER project. It presents a synthesis of the outcomes of the activities performed in Domain 2 – «Prenormative R&D for Codes and Standards» with the objective to revise and update the design rules in order to answer to some short term needs of the two projects ASTRID & MYRRHA with respect to the design and the construction of the structural components.

Several tasks within the Domain 2 of the MATTER project were devoted to the improvement of selected design rules contained in present-day C&S for which uncertainties existed with respect to GEN-IV reactor materials and operating conditions. The recommendations issued by these tasks have been summarized and presented in the respective chapters of this report. They are further discussed in view of their possible inclusion in the selected C&S. Suggestions on how to improve them are given when necessary.

The outcomes of these activities have paved the way for further development of present-day C&S, the main reserve being the necessity to perform additional experimental tests, either to support the justification of the proposed rules or to extend their domain of validity. The principal issue in this case is the long duration of experimental tests like those required for creep or thermal ageing which could not be performed in the limited timeframe of the MATTER and for which very few data exist in (open) literature.

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1 Introduction

This report constitutes the deliverable D4.8 – «Synthesis of the recommendations» of the Work Package 4 - «Design Rules» of the MATTER project. It presents a synthesis of the outcomes of the activities performed in Domain 2 – «Prenormative R&D for Codes and Standards» with the objective to revise and update the design rules in order to answer to some short term needs of the two projects ASTRID & MYRRHA with respect to the design and the construction of the structural components.

Most of the work was devoted to the design rules for 9%Cr steel grade 91 (P91/T91), a particular material with a cyclic softening behaviour and a low uniform ductility at high temperature, whose mechanical behaviour is considerably different from that of austenitic steels contained in nuclear Codes and Standards (C&S). R&D has been carried out to understand the consequences of this behaviour on the material performance with respect to different damage mechanisms like creep, creep-fatigue and ratcheting. In the framework of the MATTER project, it was envisaged to perform the final step of the R&D activity, before the codification, consisting in the adaptation of the design rules for this material, the provision of related mechanical design properties and the update of welding and fabrication requirement on the bases of the knowledge produced by the material researchers and on the industrial current practice.

At the same time, austenitic steels, in particular the different 316 grades remain the material of choice for the vessel and the piping systems and all construction requirements need to be updated according to the current industrial practice and knowledge. Also, a service lifetime of 60 years is envisaged which needs an update of available design properties and an analysis of a possible reconsideration of ageing phenomena in the design.

This report is organized as follows:

- Chapter 2 recalls the rationale of the MATTER project and provides an overview of scope and objectives of the activities.
- Chapters 3, 4, 5; 6 and 7 synthetize the outcomes of the MATTER tasks devoted to recommendations on improvements of selected design rules for gen-IV nuclear reactor components.
- Chapter 8 discusses the outcomes of these tasks with respect to the possibility of including the recommendations in the considered C&S and provides suggestions on how to further complete or improve the work.
- Chapter 9 provides an overall conclusion to the work performed in DM2.

2 Overview of Domain 2 activities on design rules improvement

The 2010-2012 implementation plan of the European Sustainable Nuclear Industrial Initiative (ESNII), in the frame of the Sustainable Nuclear Energy Technology Platform (SNETP) [1], establishes the road map for the start of construction of the European Gen IV prototypes.

Although significant differences exist among the various reactor concepts under consideration in Europe, the operational conditions envisaged for those systems are quite demanding and significantly different from the service conditions of the most commercial reactors operating today. The structural components of innovative nuclear systems will undergo service conditions which can be summarized as follows:

- exposure to higher temperatures
- higher neutron doses
- aggressive environments

The behaviour of materials under operation conditions of such systems is not appropriately covered by the available testing and evaluation standards, which therefore require updates of existing standard procedures and sometimes development of new ones. In addition, one of the required features for the success of the Gen IV reactors is the demonstration of their long lifetime: up to 60 years.

In this context, it appeared necessary to start well targeted researches, by means of European collaborations, to perform careful studies of materials behaviours in GEN-IV operational conditions and to find out criteria for the correct use of these materials in relevant reactor applications. Aim of the MATTER Project, which involved 27 partners throughout the world, was to complement the materials researches, in the frame of the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA) guidelines. The EERA has been established in 2009 regrouping several scientific representatives from research institutions all around Europe with the purpose to foster and perform material studies for nuclear applications.

More specifically, the Domain 2 - «Prenormative R&D for Codes and Standards», focuses on design rules needs of the two projects officially launched: ASTRID (Advanced Sodium Test reactor for Industrial Demonstration) & MYRRHA (Multi-purpose hYbrid Research Reactor for High-tech Application). Although the results will also be relevant for the LWR and GFR demonstrators, that should be launched later. The progress beyond the state of the art for the pre-normative R&D is to answer to some short term needs of these two projects with respect to the design and the construction of the structural components with a consensus at the European level.

Several codes for design rules are developed in Europe, more or less adapted to the design and the fabrication of the GEN IV reactors:

- In France, the RCC-MRx [2] is now the reference C&S for Gen-IV reactors. RCC-MRx has replaced RCC-MR which was written to collect the feedback on the design and construction of Superphenix. RCC-MR was adopted by the European countries (France, Italy, Great Britain and Germany) involved in the project EFR (European Fast breeder Reactor), with the support of the WGCS (Working Group on Codes & Standards from the European Commission). RCC-MR gained international recognition since it was chosen by India for the construction of PFBR and its four future fast reactors whose divergences are planned before the end of 2020. ITER, in the beginning of the Nineties, chose the RCC-MR as the basis to develop IISDC (ITER Interim Structure Design Criteria, now ISDC-IC: ITER Structural Design Criteria – In-Vessel Components), for the design of the TOKAMAK internal structures which are strongly irradiated and, similarly, by 2004, ITER has chosen the last RCC-MR edition (2007- RCC-MR) for the design and fabrication of the TOKAMAK vacuum vessel. RCC-MRx is the result of the merging of RCC-MR with the CEA code called RCC-MX for research reactors and their devices. RCC-MRx includes

new materials (aluminium and zirconium alloys) and rules for high temperature operation and irradiated components.

- Rules R5 have been developed in UK for the design of components for high temperature application. It also includes defect assessment methodologies. Material procurement, fabrication, welding and examination are not covered by these rules.

The RCC-MRx code, in particular, is the reference code selected for the design and construction of ASTRID and MYRRHA. One major innovation introduced in these two projects was the use of the ferritic/martensitic steel P91 (9%Cr steel) for the steam generator and the core support plate. Even if the use of this material has now been reconsidered by the two projects (alloy 800 is now the reference for the ASTRID steam generator and 316LN for MYRRHA core support plate), grade 91 is still the reference vessel material for ALLEGRO and for the heat exchangers and steam generators for ALFRED. In some other international projects, it is still the reference material for circuits and heat exchangers (PFBR, JSRF, ...)

All rules of the RCC-MR and R5 have mainly been validated for austenitic stainless steels. The P91 is a particular material with a cyclic softening behaviour and a low uniform ductility at high temperature. A lot of R&D programs have been realised to understand the consequences of this behaviour on the material performance under different loading conditions. In the frame of MATTER, it was envisaged to perform the final step of the R&D activity, before the codification, consisting in the adaptation of the design rules for this material, the provision of related mechanical design properties and the update of welding and fabrication requirement on the basis of the knowledge produced by the material researchers and on the industrial current practice.

For ASTRID the key issues are strongly linked with high temperature and extended life-duration. For MYRRHA, they are dependant of coolant-material interaction effects and in particular liquid metal embrittlement. These last points were investigated specifically in deliverables D5.2 [3] and D5.5 [4]. It is however outside the scope of this report, since RCC-MRx does not include explicit rules to take into account corrosion/erosion effects, relying on an appropriate selection of materials and control of chemical compositions. The only recommendation is that if the component is subject to in-service thinning resulting from surface corrosion or under the effects of products handled or environmental conditions, a certain additional thickness shall be provided.

At the same time, 316SS remains the material for the vessel and the piping systems and all construction requirements need to be updated according to the current industrial practice and knowledge. Also, a service lifetime of 60 years is envisaged which needs an update of available design properties and an analysis of a possible reconsideration of ageing phenomena in the design. RCC-MRx already accounts for ageing phenomena by the introduction of an ageing factor that further reduces allowable stress. However, explicit values are not yet given for the materials of interest.

Consequently, with respect to design rules contained in the selected C&S, the following issues were investigated in the corresponding tasks of DM2:

- Task 4.2 – Ratcheting rules for P91
- Task 4.3 – Creep and creep-fatigue interaction for P91 components.
- Task 5.2 – Recommendation for the negligible creep domain for P91 and 316SS
- Task 5.3 – Additional design factors

- Task 6.1 – P91 and 316SS weld coefficients

The outcomes from these tasks are summarized and discussed in the following chapters.

3 Recommendations on ratcheting Rules for P91

Ratcheting is by definition the accumulation of plastic deformation in structures subjected to cyclic stressing above the yield limit with a non-zero primary stress. When a structure is subjected to cyclic loading, it may show signs of permanent deformation at the end of the first cycle. During subsequent cycles the following cases may arise:

- Plastic adaptation (shakedown): the structure is said to be plastically adapted if, after a few cycles, its behaviour becomes elastic at every point in the structure.
- Plastic accommodation: the structure undergoes plastic accommodation if, after a few cycles, its behaviour, while remaining elastoplastic, is the same at each cycle. Plastic accommodation excludes the possibility of progressive deformation.
- Global plastic adaptation (overall shakedown): global plastic adaptation (overall shakedown) is the state of a structure which undergoes plastic accommodation and in which: plastic strain only appears in strain concentration zones whose dimensions are less than the length of the supporting line segments of the sections under consideration. In this state, the response of the structure is generally elastic and the development of plastic strain is inhibited by restraint ensured by the parts which remain elastic. The strain concentration effect depends mainly on geometry, loading and the material behaviour law.
- Progressive deformation: in the absence of creep and for purely elastic and plastic behaviour, the definition of progressive deformation or ratchet is easy. There is progressive deformation if an increase of deformation appears at each cycle under the effect of cyclic loads. This phenomenon is different from adaptation in which, after application of a few cycles, the structure retains the same geometry. When creep is involved, and consequently the time-related phenomena, this type of simple definition is no longer adequate. In RCC-MRx, progressive deformation is used to designate the increase in the deformation due to loads caused by imposed cyclic deformations.

A detailed review of the rules used in present-day nuclear C&S to prevent progressive deformation has been performed in [5]. Two rules are proposed in RCC-MRx the «3Sm» rule and the «efficiency diagram» rule. The 3Sm criterion for 9%Cr steels is conservative but extremely severe, preventing plastic deformation even when the cyclic softening of the material is taken into account. Note that the 3Sm rule can only be used, according to the code, when creep is negligible.

On the other hand, the efficiency diagram criterion used in RCC-MRx has been developed in order to allow a limited amount of cumulative strain to take place without compromising the lifetime of the material [6]. By allowing a limited amount of plastic deformation to occur, this method is in principle less conservative than the 3Sm rule. It also allows taking into account the effects of

thermal ratcheting (i.e. ratcheting with no primary membrane stress) and overloads of short duration.

The basis of the efficiency diagram is however empirical since it is constructed starting from experimental tests as a lower envelope of the worst results. It should therefore be validated whenever a new material is used, especially if the strain hardening behaviour changes substantially. In fact, the efficiency diagram rule has proven not conservative for 9%Cr steels and this is one of the reasons why in the present edition of the code these steels have been moved to the probationary rules section (Tome 6).

For the construction of the diagram, the effective primary stress (P_{eff}) is defined as the primary stress that, when acting alone, would give using the monotonic stress-strain curve, the same cumulative strain observed at failure with a superposed cyclic primary and secondary load. The results of experimental tests are then represented on the space of the two variables $V = P/P_{eff}$ (efficiency index) and $SR = \Delta Q/P$ (secondary ratio), where:

-) P is the equivalent primary (constant) stress
-) ΔQ is the equivalent elastic secondary stress range acting on the specimens.

The efficiency diagram is then constructed as the lower envelope curve representing the «worst» results in order to obtain a conservative estimated P_{eff} using the ratio of loads $SR = \Delta Q/P$.

The efficiency diagram presently given in the RCC-MRx code has in fact been constructed and validated starting from a considerable number of results of experimental test (tension-torsion, internal pressure-axial deformation, etc.), at different temperatures and with or without hold times (creep), but performed mainly on austenitic stainless steels (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Experimental base used to construct and validate the efficiency diagram presently in the RCC-MRx code.

Using the efficiency diagram, the limitation of the ratcheting consists then in defining an allowable value for the effective primary stress P_{eff} . This value corresponds to a maximum allowable cumulative strain than can be determined on the monotonic tension curve. The efficiency diagram allows to express a limit on the allowable strain as a limit on the stress that can be calculated starting from the results of elastic analysis.

The final results of the work performed in task 4.2 are reported in [7]. On the basis of the tension-torsion ratcheting tests performed in task 7.1 [8] as well as other results available in literature [9], a new efficiency diagram is proposed for P91 and other 9%Cr steel which represents the “worst case” envelope of the obtained result. The equations describing the new diagram have been determined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 SR \leq 0.45 & & V &= 1 \\
 0.45 < SR \leq 4 & & V &= 1.1 - \frac{1.15 \times SR^2}{(1 + SR)^2} \\
 SR > 4 & & V &= \frac{0.98}{SR^{0.72}}
 \end{aligned}$$

The new diagram is shown in Figure 2 and compared with the one used for austenitic steels.

Figure 2: New efficiency diagram proposed for P91 and 9%Cr steels.

The adaptation of the efficiency diagram criterion to 9%Cr steels implies however not only the development of a new efficiency diagram but also the definition of appropriate limits for P_{eff} . In order to limit ratcheting, the efficiency diagram criterion defines limits on the effective primary stress P_{eff} that implicitly correspond to strain limitations. These limits are expressed as multiples of the maximum allowable primary stress S_m : $k \cdot S_m$. However, since the stress-strain relation depends on the material, the same values of k lead to different cumulative strains depending on the material. In RCC-MRx, for 316L(N), the limits on P_{eff} correspond to a maximum cumulative strain of 1% for membrane stresses and 1.7% for membrane plus bending stresses. This is no longer true in case of 9%Cr steels: in particular, with k equal to 1.3 the limit on P_m does not correspond to 1% strain as for austenitic steels, but about 0.1% instead. The material still has an elastic behaviour. Under these conditions, there is no ratcheting phenomenon and therefore no question about limitation of ratcheting, obviously the criterion is overly conservative.

To define limits on P_{eff} suited for 9%Cr steels, a procedure is used that consists in relating the efficiency diagram rule to the theoretical $2S_y$ limit that prevents ratcheting in a perfectly-plastic material, but using the cyclic stress-strain curve in order to take into account the softening behavior of the material (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Determination of a «softened» S_y limit on the reduced cyclic stress-strain curve.

Using this procedure, two limits are proposed one for the effective primary stress calculated from membrane stress alone (P_1) and one for the effective primary stress calculated from membrane plus bending stresses (P_2):

$$P_1 \leq 1,85 \times S_m$$

$$P_2 \leq 2 \times S_m$$

The assumed limits give, in the most unfavourable cases, a membrane strain of 0.15% and a membrane+bending strain of 0.31%.

The proposed rule has further been validated using the results of the structural thermal ratcheting tests performed in ENEA consisting of a cylinder that is cyclically subjected to a temperature gradient traveling in the axial direction with no primary loads applied (Figure 4). The situation is representative of the ratcheting due to the variations of the free level of the coolant on the reactor vessel of a molten metal reactor: during the operation the coolant level moves up and down cyclically and the walls of the reactor vessel are cyclically subjected to a traveling axial temperature distribution. The stresses exerted on the structure are mainly linked to the movement of the axial thermal gradient since at the free surface the primary stresses are low or negligible.

Figure 4: Schematic view of the experimental apparatus.

Values of P_{eff} have been calculated on the basis of the measured circumferential plastic deformation of the specimen and corresponding stress levels calculated by FE simulations. Results have been represented on the efficiency diagram as shown in Figure 5. It can be seen that all the points are located above the new efficiency diagram proposed for 9Cr steels, while they are below the one defined for austenitic steels. This confirms that the new diagram represents in fact the envelope of the worst cases, i.e. the total deformation predicted by the diagram is conservative and it can effectively be used to limit ratcheting in 9Cr steels.

Figure 5: Validation of the proposed efficiency diagram rule for thermal ratcheting.

4 Recommendations on creep and creep-fatigue interaction for P91 components

Creep-fatigue (CF) damage can be evaluated using the rules and guidelines provided in the existing design codes, such as ASME III NH, RCC-MRx and BS-R5. The models and methodologies included currently in design codes utilize the creep-fatigue interaction diagram and the methods differ in the way how the creep and fatigue damage fractions are calculated. These procedures use the results of creep tests to determine the creep damage-accumulation models, which are subsequently applied to predict damage in creep-fatigue cycling and in particular strain-controlled dwells that arise during steady operation within a thermal cycle.

The interaction diagram approach is based on separate creep and fatigue assessments where the interaction is taken into account by the interaction diagram. The diagram does not have a clear physical basis and the scatter in the predictions is quite large. For time-fraction approaches, the rupture strength of the material is used to calculate creep damage, while in the ductility-exhaustion approach the creep ductility is used to calculate creep damage.

The interaction diagram for P91 as defined by RCC-MRx probationary phase rules and ASME-NH is presented in Figure 6 with the creep damage defined as t/t_r (where t is the hold time at a given stress and t_r the corresponding time to creep rupture) and the fatigue fraction as N_f/N_{f0} (where N_f is the number of cycles at a given strain range $\Delta\varepsilon$ and N_{f0} the corresponding number of cycles to failure). In design rules the N_{f0} is not generally the experimentally measured number of cycles to failure, but rather the allowable number of cycles for design taking into account appropriate margins (see also §7.1 for the construction of the fatigue «design» curve). It is important to keep

in mind that the clearly different interaction locus points are not describing a different view of material endurance between the codes but is a product of entirely different calculation methodologies for creep damage accumulation. Additionally, the RCC-MRx locus point (0.3,0.3) should be taken as a probationary phase rule.

Figure 6. The creep-fatigue Interaction diagram for P91 as defined by nuclear codes.

A number of methods were compared for the predicting the creep-fatigue life of P91 steel in [10]. It has been shown that the time fraction approach for interaction (using RCC-MRx locus point (0.3,0.3), which is now in the probationary phase rules of the code) performs satisfactorily and that the classical ductility exhaustion method (DE) predicts extensive creep damage. The modified ductility based versions (SMDE and EMDE) performed better than the classical approach. A strain rate modified (SRM) model with time dependent damage accumulation also shows promise for use in creep-fatigue interaction diagrams.

The RCC-MRx creep strain rules do not take the material characteristics, such as cyclic softening for P91 steel, directly into account. During the MATTER project, a small creep test programme was performed by JRC with pre-fatigued test specimen. The results show that the pre-fatigue has affected the creep life and the secondary creep strain rate of the material. The increase in strain rate due to softening may be problematic for designing with creep strain limitations. There is a possibility that the softening ratio could be used as a "damage" factor for estimating the loss of creep strength in the softened material. However, it seems that the creep strain model in RCC-MRx probationary phase rules would predict satisfactorily to about 0.5% creep strain even for the softened material. From the creep-fatigue stand point this is also not a major problem since a decreased amount of relaxation will increase the predicted creep time fraction, thus adding conservatism in the CF prediction. Furthermore, the interaction diagram is intended to add conservatism into creep-fatigue evaluation by applying the non-unity (e.g. (0.3,0.3) in RCC-MRx for P91 steel) locus point.

An alternative approach is also considered in [11], based on the observation that that the bulk of available CF data for P91 is based on experimental results obtained for short hold times with high stresses, while real conditions in nuclear plants are quite the opposite (long hold times with low stresses). The use of creep amplified strain range and the LCF fatigue curves is thus not really an option since it is rather clear that it will surely not take the long term creep cavitation damage into account. Another option for simplified CF calculations in the code is to use the CF models either based on the defined LCF curve or CF and creep rupture properties instead of the interaction diagram approach.

One of the simplified models applied in the MATTER to predict the creep-fatigue cyclic life is the Manson-Halford model (MH-CF) [12], [13]:

$$N_{CF}(t_h) = \frac{N_{f0}}{1 + \frac{k}{\frac{A}{t_h} \cdot (N_{f0})^{\frac{m+b}{m}}}}$$

The model parameters A and m are derived from the creep rupture model of the material. The parameter m is the slope of $d\log(\sigma)/d\log(t_r)$ of the creep model and A the rupture time at a specified reference stress. The reference stress used for P91 was the 75% ultimate tensile strength (R_m) at the specified temperature. The material constant k is found by fitting to available creep-fatigue data. The parameter b is retrieved from the $\Delta\varepsilon$ - N_{f0} curve by extracting the elastic exponent of the Manson-Coffin equation. The material parameter k is expected to be dependent on the type of control. The parameters for P91 at 550°C and 600°C optimized on the JAEA data are given in [14]. Note that t_h is to be given in hours and model is predicting strain controlled CF lives only.

It should be noted that the MH-CF model also needs the LCF cycles to failure as input. The LCF Manson-Coffin model for cycles to failure N_{f0} is defined as:

$$N_{f0} = \left[\frac{(\Delta\varepsilon - C_1)}{C_2} \right]^{1/C_3}$$

Where C_i are the fitting parameters and $\Delta\varepsilon$ is the total strain range.

The parameters for the Manson-Halford model are given Table 1. The LCF model parameters are given in Table 2.

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Temperature (°C)	A(T)	m	b	k
550	10	-0.0783	0.12	0.07904
600	0.6			

Table 1. Parameters for the MH-CF model at 550°C, $\log(A) = -0.0236 \cdot T + 13.961$ for interpolation use in the range of 550-600°C only.

Temp. (°C)	c ₁	c ₂	c ₃
550 (MATTER)	0.27472	19.17968	-0.46885
550 (JAEA)	0.23976	33.39224	-0.52268
600 (MATTER)	0.24	148.6077	-0.72138
625 EPRI	0.24	142.2743	-0.76605

Table 2. Parameters for the Manson-Coffin model. Parameters optimized on JAEA, MATTER and EPRI (625°C) data.

The Φ -model [15], [16] is based on the assumption that there exists a reference stress σ_{ref} multilinearly definable in strain range $\Delta\varepsilon$, temperature T and hold time t_h that predicts a creep rupture time equal to the combined hold times in a CF test. The model is using the Wilshire equation [17] for creep as base.

The reference normalized stress $\Phi_{CF} (\sigma_{ref}/R_m)$ for Φ -model is defined as:

$$\Phi_{CF}(\Delta\varepsilon, t_h, T) = A_1 + \frac{A_2}{\Delta\varepsilon} + A_3 \cdot \log(t_h) + A_4 \cdot T$$

The Wilshire normalized stress σ/R_m for rupture strength is defined as:

$$\frac{\sigma}{R_m} = \exp \left[-k(t_r \cdot \exp(\frac{-Q}{R \cdot T}))^u \right]$$

Using the above equation and rewriting the sum of hold times causing cyclic failure becomes:

$$\sum t_h = - \left(\frac{\Phi_{CF}(\Delta\varepsilon, t_h, T)}{k} \right)^{1/u} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{Q_c^*}{RT}\right)$$

And the number of cycles is simply:

$$N_f = \frac{\sum t_h}{t_h}$$

The parameters needed for using the Φ -model for predicting CF cycles to failure are given in Table 4 (creep rupture parameters for the Wilshire equation in Table 3).

Model type	$\sigma/R_m > 0.45$		$\sigma/R_m \leq 0.45$	
	k	u	k	u
rupture	82.769102	0.135627	75.618032	0.133624

Table 3. Wilshire creep rupture model parameters for P91 steel (NIMS data [18]). Note that time ($t_{r/e}$) is in hours, and the total strain range in %. Note also that there is a change in parameters at the stress ratio of 0.45. The activation energy Q is 300 000 J/mol in all cases.

A1	A2	A3	A4
1.98016	-0.06706	-0.07629	-0.00162

Table 4. Parameters for the Φ -model. The parameters are optimized on JAEA data [14]. The temperature range is 450-650°C.

At the end of the report [11] the following recommendations are made:

1. Tests performed in MATTER project and recent studies indicate that the creep behaviour of P91 steel is deteriorated after cyclic loadings. However, the assessment methods in codes do not take this effect properly into account. For example, in the RCC-MRx probationary phase rules the creep strain equations for primary and secondary creep region are provided for defined stress-time-temperature range along with fitting constants, but the cyclic history is not taken into account in that procedure. A way to improve the creep strain assessment in codes would be to implement a creep strain model, such as LCSP model, which limits the time to strain to a maximum value of a specified time to rupture. This approach would make corrections for softening/hardening or "creep damage" history simpler, for instance by introducing correction factors. The application of damage history of course further complicates the use of any model with the creep-fatigue interaction diagram. The main implication of the softening is not for creep-fatigue interaction in the

RCC-MRx code, but rather for pure creep design. In the case of creep-fatigue an underestimation of creep rate will cause higher creep damage factors due to higher stresses to be used for creep rupture determination. Applied in the interaction diagram the result is more conservative limits for the allowable number of cycles.

2. The interaction diagram models are at the time the only type of models currently applied in design codes. The simplified models optimized for P91 seem to be very promising and they robustly predict cycles to failure with as good or superior performance. The equations of the simplified methods are also easy to implement for strain range, temperature and hold time dependent allowable cycle predictions. The new methodology would totally avoid the question of the multitude of variations for "creep damage" calculated for a cycle that is assumed to be representative for the whole test. Also the impact of softening/hardening and the somewhat arbitrarily defined interaction locus in the interaction diagram would be avoided.
3. For creep-fatigue assessment using interaction diagram based models or the recommended new simplified methods, the majority of currently available data for modelling and validation is situated in the regime of relatively large strain ranges and short hold periods, where the induced "creep damage" for the data is mainly strain and is not really affected by creep damage (cavitation) in the grain boundaries. The extrapolation to "long term" type of creep damage is thus somewhat questionable with the present available data. To properly validate either the interaction diagram based methods or the simplified methods, test data with long hold periods (in stress and strain control) is required. The tensile properties of softened material from both LCF and CF tests at different locations in the softening curve also need to be thoroughly determined to further investigate the high creep strain rates measured in CF tests with stress controlled hold times. The long to very long hold time tests may also improve the understanding of the long term microstructural evolution in cyclic service.

By applying the recommendation 1 the creep behaviour and creep component in the interaction diagram based method may be more accurately described. Recommendation 2 provides an alternative to the interaction diagram based creep-fatigue evaluation. Recommendation 3 is considered necessary for all evaluation and modelling methods.

5 Recommendations on the negligible creep domain for P91 and 316SS

Negligible creep (NEC) design curves define temperatures and associated reference stresses where creep effects can be considered insignificant. With these limits reliably defined, the component design at temperatures below the ones generally tested for creep becomes clearer and considerably easier. The concept of negligible creep is shown in Figure 7. Negligible creep temperature curves (T_{NEC}) need of course to be supported by tests and associated models. A general challenge for determining the T_{NEC} for grade 91 ferritic-martensitic steel is that there is very little data available at the border of or in the actual negligible creep regime. In the current

version of the RCC-MRx there is generally accepted negligible creep limits for the austenitic steel 316L(N) but not for P91.

Figure 7: Time-temperature regions for specified reference stress. The Negligible Creep temperature curve T_{NEC} (long dash) separates the regions where time dependent and time independent design has to be applied. The creep rupture temperature curve beyond which creep failure occurs (continuous line) and the No Creep limit (small dash) at 375°C are also given.

In MATTER work package 5 the negligible temperature curve of P91 was constructed with a reference stress of 0.56 times the ultimate tensile strength based on the RCC-MRx allowable stress definition [19]. For the determination of the negligible creep range both data collected from literature [20,21,22] and the data generated within the project were used. It was shown that limiting the allowed creep strain below 0.2% is counterproductive in terms of data availability and model prediction robustness.

The proposed NC criterion was therefore set as 0.2% in strain. The T_{NEC} curve could be defined by the Wilshire equation for time to specified strain as given by:

$$t_{\varepsilon} = \left[-\frac{1}{k} \ln\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{UTS}}\right) \right]^{\frac{1}{u}} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{Q}{R \cdot T}\right)$$

where σ is the test stress and σ_{UTS} the ultimate tensile strength, i.e. σ/σ_{UTS} is the normalized stress, Q the activation energy, R the gas constant and T the temperature in K.

The WE model fits for rupture, 1%, 0.5%, 0.2% strain (NIMS data only) are shown in Figure 8 and the corresponding model parameters derived from the plot are shown in Figure 9 and Table 3.

The full master strain model for stresses above $0.45 \cdot R_m$ and strains in the range of 0.2-1% is defined with k and u as functions of strain. The functions for k and u are given in Table 6.

Figure 8. NIMS strain data and WE model predictions for rupture, 1%, 0.5% and 0.2% strain.

Figure 9. Determination of fitting parameters u and k for the strain data.

Model type	$\sigma/R_m > 0.45$		$\sigma/R_m \leq 0.45$	
	k	u	k	u
rupture	82.769102	0.135627	75.618032	0.133624

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1.0% strain	150.827655	0.141074	31.330443	0.101257
0.5% strain	246.987398	0.147260	22.206093	0.086804
0.2% strain	382.358129	0.149313	33.303955	0.090673

Table 5. Wilshire creep strain and rupture model parameters for P91 steel (NIMS data). Note that time ($t_{r/\epsilon}$) is in hours, and the total strain range in %. Note also that there is a change in parameters at the stress ratio of 0.45. The activation energy Q is 300 000 J/mol in all cases.

$\sigma/R_m > 0.45$ predicted		
Strain range % (0.2-1%)	$k = -331.71 \cdot \log(\epsilon)$	$u = -1.051 \cdot \epsilon + 0.1518$

Table 6. Wilshire creep strain parameters k and u for full master strain model ($\epsilon_c \leq 1\%$, $T=375-600^\circ\text{C}$ and $\sigma/R_m > 0.45$). Note that ϵ is not to be given in %.

The proposed criteria for NC and the corresponding reference stresses are given in Table 7 and the proposed T_{NEC} curve for P91 is given in Figure 10. Note that the proposed T_{NEC} curve crosses the temperature limit of time independent design (375°C) at a service life of about 500 000 hours.

It is to be remembered that there is extensive extrapolation involved in defining the T_{NEC} curve and the corresponding time factors. If the extrapolation range would be limited to a factor of 3 as recommended when defining the creep rupture properties, the curve could not be defined.

The conservativeness of the generated T_{NEC} curve based on time to 0.2% creep strain is large when compared to rupture. Rupture times are >1000 times higher than the time to 0.2% strain at the reference stress level. When the predicted rupture times at reference stress (0.56 R_m) and allowable stress (1/2.7 R_m) are compared, an additional safety of 142 in time is imposed, thus concluding that the proposed T_{NEC} curve has a "sufficient" safety margin against creep.

It is to be noted that additional creep tests are highly recommended to verify the results with a closer range of stresses around the reference stress.

Figure 10. Proposed negligible creep temperature curve for the 0.2% creep strain criterion with reference stresses of $0.56 \cdot R_m$ with correction for RCC-MRx average rupture strength. Note that the curve is intersecting the NC temperature (375°C) at approximately 500 000 h.

Based on:	Reference stress	NEC criterion
Creep strain $\epsilon_c \leq 0.2\%$	$1.5 \cdot S_m$ ($0.56 \cdot R_m$)	$\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{t_i}{t_{i-\max}} \right) \leq 1$
Time factor $t \leq t_r/1000$	$1.5 \cdot S_m$ ($0.56 \cdot R_m$)	$\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{t_i}{t_{i-\max}} \right) \leq 1$

Table 7. P91 negligible creep definition to be proposed for RCC-MRx with $S_m = R_m/2.7$

6 Recommendations on additional design factors

As recalled in §2, operating conditions of nuclear components in GEN-IV reactors will differ from those of GEN-II/III reactors: operating temperatures will be significantly higher, proposed coolants potentially more corrosive and irradiation damage on the employed materials more intense. Moreover, qualification of material for GEN-IV reactors needs the demonstration of their behaviour until 60 years, compared to the 40 years lifetime of past projects. Under these conditions, additional degradation phenomena might appear that can affect the integrity of structures.

In report [3], thermal ageing and creep, interactions with sodium or oxygen-containing lead alloys as well as irradiation damage were identified as phenomena that potentially compromise the lifetime of steel components in GEN-IV nuclear reactors, and may require more specific

consideration in codes and standards. Design curves of fundamental strength properties may have to be reviewed if safety margins are still sufficient when degradation of material performance due to the named phenomena occurs and increases with time. Design rules may have to be modified or newly defined only if degradation goes beyond a plain reduction in strength, entirely new damage modes arise and so far acceptable simplifications in the analysis of the expected component behaviour over service time seem no longer applicable.

The two additional degradation modes within the scope of this report, namely thermal ageing and irradiation effects are further discussed in the following sub-chapters.

6.1 Thermal Ageing

Thermal ageing is related to the stability of the material microstructure at high service temperatures. When brought to this temperature, a variety of processes may occur, including plain grain growth of the material matrix, coarsening of particles of secondary phases, segregation of minor material constituents at the material surface or internal interfaces (e.g., grain boundaries), dissolution of precipitates and formation of new phases not present in the initial microstructure. In order to limit the occurrence of these phenomena, and the consequent degradation of mechanical properties, the importance of the metallurgical parameters as well as the fabrication route of the different pieces is essential, as explained in [3]. It concerns base metal but also weldments.

For example, continuous optimizations have been performed in the French SFR past projects to reach the 316L(N) RCC-MRx grade. They concern optimizations of the chemical composition but also a control of the fabrication parameters. Through these parameters (both chemical composition and fabrication route), the microstructural state of component will be defined and will determine the mechanical behaviour in as received conditions but also during the in service life. Tighter specifications on chemical composition for 316L(N) [alloy 1S in Appendix A3 of RCC-MRx] allow to obtain products with very low delta ferrite content (less than 1%) as illustrated on Figure 11. This fact is obtained by a controlled balance between α and γ forming elements including narrow specification on Ni, Cr and Mo elements compared to ASME specification (Table 8). Also, tighter specifications are given in relation to fabrication parameters such as heat treatment conditions, cooling rate, and cold working factors.

Regarding 9Cr F/M steels as Grade 91, due to their complex microstructure which is not stable at service temperatures, a lot of microstructural evolutions will occur and induce mechanical properties evolutions. Moreover, it is important also to notice that the primary microstructure due to solidification will induce some non-reversible behaviour for steel (with respect to the prior austenite grain size and associated precipitation) even if the final quality heat treatment (normalized or quenched after austenitization then tempered treatment) erases part of cold-working. So, results obtained on the final piece are partially linked to prior steps of elaboration. In fact, Codes and Standards are not very prescriptive regarding these prior steps which depend more specifically on steelmakers' knowledge.

The same considerations on the optimization of the chemical composition also apply to the choice of appropriate filler metals for welding.

Figure 11: Price and Andrew diagram showing the different areas for 316L and 316L(N) with respect to the chemical composition specification.

	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Ni	Cr	Mo	Al	N	Co	B (ppm)
X2CrNiMo17-12-2	≤0,03	≤1.0	≤2.0	<0.045	<0,015	10-13	16.5-18.5	2.0-2.5	-	≤0.1	-	-
316L ASME	<0.03	≤0.75	≤2.0	≤0.045	≤0.030	10-14	16-18	2.0-3.0	-	≤0.1	-	-
316L(N) RCC-MRx	≤0,03	≤0.50	1.6-2.0	≤0,03	≤0,015	12.0-12.5	17-18	2.3-2.7	-	0.06-0.08	<1	≤ 20
316LN ASME	≤0,03	≤0.75	≤2.0	≤0.045	≤0.030	10-14	16-18	2.0-3.0	-	0.10-0.16	-	-
316FR JSME [23]	≤0,02	≤1.0	≤2.0	0.020-0.045	≤0,030	10-14	16-18	2.0-3.0	≤0,05	0.06-0.12	-	-

Table 8: Chemical composition of different 316 grades in nuclear C&S (Weight %)

Generally speaking, thermal ageing mainly affects the resistance, ductility properties and creep properties of the materials. During creep test, material is submitted both to microstructural evolution due to ageing and to damaging due to mechanical solicitations. In laboratory, even if some long term creep tests are performed, more frequently short or medium duration for creep tests are involved. To perform this, stress and/or temperature are increased. Creep damage however is related to different phenomena: the necking model for predicting short to medium term creep fracture and a second part, for longer fracture times and lower stresses where the fracture is governed by diffusional growth and coalescence of intergranular cavities (Riedel model). This second way of degradation is more in agreement with what happens during in-service life. So, the representativeness of such tests is questionable compared to in service solicitations.

RCC-MRx accounts for ageing by the introduction of an ageing factor that further reduces allowable stress in comparison to the capabilities of the material as determined from short-term tests without particular pre-ageing of samples tested. However, no quantitative values are given for the steels of interest. In RCC-MRx, no such coefficients are supplied for 316L SS and grade 91. ASME, section III, Division1, subsection NH supplies however ageing factors (Table 9).

Material	Service Temp., °F (°C)	YS Reduction Factor	TS Reduction Factor
304SS	≥ 900 (480)	1.00	0.80
316SS	≥ 900 (480)	1.00	0.80
800H	≥ 1,350 (730)	0.90	0.90
2¼ Cr-1Mo	≥ 800 (425)	[Note (1)]	[Note (1)]
9Cr-1Mo-V	≥ 900 (480)	1.0	[Note (2)]

GENERAL NOTE: No reduction factor required for service below the indicated temperature.

NOTES:
 (1) See Tables NH-3225-3A and NH-3225-3B are selected to correspond to the maximum wall-averaged temperature achieved during any Levels A, B, or C Service Loading.
 (2) See Table NH-3225-4.

Table 9: ASME – Tensile and Yield Strength ageing coefficient for 316 SS and 9Cr-1Mo-V materials

For 316L SS, ageing does not seem to induce significant evolution of tensile properties. Regarding ductility, no or few data can be found in the open literature. For modified 9Cr-1Mo steel (as for grade 91), regarding tensile properties, ageing does not involve significant evolution of tensile properties, but ductility decreases significantly with ageing duration at temperature higher than 450°C: shift of the DBTT but also an energy reduction for the upper shelf. In view of plant operation, this may be of particular importance for re-starting operation after shutdown, accidental overloading or other events that provoke a relatively short-term response of the material, being considered in plant design on the basis of the results from short-term material tests.

More experimental data are needed to consolidate the database of properties at high temperature and long durations to obtain relevant information concerning thermal ageing. Test at higher temperatures can be used to accelerate degradation mechanisms and reduce the testing time, but in this case one must be sure that new degradation phenomena do not appear since this would invalidate the results. On the base of an engineer approach, data are needed on at least 1/3 of the life time and the creep or ageing temperature should not exceed 25°C from in service one [24]. More precisely, 40 years lifetime (280 000h of operation) requires experimental test of 11 years (93 000h) and 60 years lifetimes (420 000 h of operation) requires experimental test of 16 years (140 000h). Of course, this kind of tests could not be performed in the limited timeframe of the MATTER project.

Considering the difficulties of obtaining experimental data, work has focused on determining the best options for extrapolating already available results [4]. For correlating the change in strength properties with ageing temperature T (in K) and time t, a common tempering parameter:

$$R=A - B [T (C + \log t)]$$

is suggested that gives the strength ratio between aged and initial state. A, B and C are constants, the latter of which has a value of 10. Values for A and B are not explicitly stated, but, apparently, have been evaluated for temperature ranging from 482 to 704°C and time up to 75,000 h [25].

As regards the creep life reduction, the damage time fraction approach can still be used, but the problem is to account for the reduced rupture time from the aging. Another approach is to use the Monkman-Grant (MG) model where the rupture life is related to the minimum creep rate:

$$t_r = A\dot{\epsilon}_{min}^p$$

Both aged and unaged material seem to follow the MG relationship quite well as shown in Figure 4, but, for prediction, the increase in minimum creep rate for the aged material is needed.

Figure 12: Predicted life for unexposed and aged material using the Monkman-Grant model [26]

The API 579 Omega damage model has also been used. In this approach, the creep damage factor and creep rates are calculated using a general damage factor Ω :

$$D_{\Omega} = \dot{\epsilon}\Omega t / (1 + \dot{\epsilon}\Omega t) \text{ where } \dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_0 \exp(\Omega \epsilon)$$

$\dot{\epsilon}_0$ is the initial creep rate, and Ω represents the combined effect of the microstructural evolution. A weakness with this approach is that Ω is purely empirical and it does not distinguish between different ageing mechanisms. Its use for extrapolation is questionable.

A more mechanistic approach proposed by Dyson [27] actually incorporates the various microstructural features. This model is based on quantities that can be measured or computed from physics-based models and, hence, much better suited for extrapolation. The price is of course the much higher complexity and that it requires knowledge of the microstructural evolution from observations or models. Although these more advanced models cannot be used as Design Rules, they could be very useful as a tool to justify ageing factors. One could also consider a combination of models such as using the Dyson or Omega model to derive the minimum creep rate, and Monkman-Grant to finally estimate the rupture life.

6.2 Effects of irradiation

Common interactions between irradiation, in the sense of high-energy particles, and crystalline materials (steels) are the displacement of atoms from their original position in the crystal lattice or transmutation into other isotopes, accompanied by release of either electromagnetic radiation or small atoms like He and H. Both displacement and transmutation rates strongly depend on the type (e.g., protons or neutrons) and the energy spectrum of the radiation as well as on the irradiated material. The gaseous transmutation products, especially He, may have detrimental effects, even when the produced amounts are small [28]. The body-centred cubic alloys, including ferritic/martensitic steels, are less affected by helium embrittlement (attributed to "stress-induced growth of cavities nucleated from helium bubbles at grain boundaries") than the face-centred cubic austenitic steels [29]. The displacement of atoms or displacement cascades knocked-on by the first atom removed from its original position produce Frenkel defects, i.e., pairs of vacancies and interstitial atoms. The effects on materials properties result from consecutive processes like defect annihilation, accumulation, cavity formation, etc., and strongly depend on the temperature of irradiation relative to the melting temperature of the material. Mechanical strength may be affected by irradiation, but also changes in geometric dimensions of irradiated steel, namely swelling, may occur.

The general strategy of considering irradiation effects in design codes and standards for structural components is to first make a classification in terms of the expected significance for the component performance over the service time, i.e., (a) negligible; (b) significant and to be considered; (c) maximum allowable irradiation [30]. Respective thresholds of irradiation fluence or resulting accumulated damage on the atomic scale are material dependent, and may vary with the temperature range under consideration. If a significant impact on strength properties is to be expected, it needs to be either confirmed that design curves provided in the code still provide a sufficient safety margin or further reduced strength properties assumed. A Japanese assessment of irradiation effects on Type 316 steel (equivalent to 316LN) suggests that yield and tensile strength are largely insensitive to irradiation expected in a fast breeder reactor, but to account for a reduction in stress-rupture time (creep) by a fluence-dependent factor that is maximum 3 [31]. In view of the embrittlement of steels resulting from irradiation, a minimum ductility at the end of service time must be proven. The incorporation of irradiation effects on 9Cr steels in RCC-MRx has been recently discussed using low-activation EUORFER97 as an example [32].

7 Recommendations on P91 and 316SS weld coefficients

Since the design of structural components is influenced by the presence of the welds, their mechanical properties are also included in C&S. In design codes, a welded junction is considered as a homogeneous (base metal) component with a margin coefficient, called weld coefficient. This allows taking into account the reduced load bearing capability of the welded junction. Joint coefficients are defined with respect to the considered damage mode: monotonic loading, creep and fatigue. These weld coefficients are introduced in the design rules to reduce the weld allowable loading conditions. Within the matter project, weld coefficients for the following materials and welding techniques have been investigated:

- Fatigue joint coefficients according to RCC-MRx definition for narrow-TIG weldments of P91 steel.
- Fatigue joint coefficients according to R5 definition for 316H tube weldments in AGR boilers.
- Fatigue joint coefficients according to RCC-MRx definition for 316-LN and P91 weldments performed with the Hybrid Laser Welding techniques developed in the framework of Tasks 6.2 and 6.3.

The outcomes of these activities are presented in the following chapters.

7.1 Determination of fatigue joint coefficients for P91 steel in RCC-MRx.

A detailed review of design rules for welded joints in RCC-MRx is given in [33]. The RCC-MRx code defines appropriate criteria to guarantee safety with regard to a number of types of damages. General analysis rules for protection against these damages are provided in section RB 3200 and sub-chapters. For welded assemblies, the analysis can be performed without considering the presence of the welded joint, using the rules for homogenous materials but modifying the allowable limits by appropriate coefficients that are dependent on the welded joint characteristics (RB 3290).

Fatigue damage takes place in a material subject to a load that is cyclically repeated in time. This phenomenon frequently occurs under imposed displacement or deformation loads such as thermal gradients. Studies of this damage have shown that the variation in strain is the relevant parameter in determining the analysis criterion. In the case of multiaxial loads, the RCC-MR recommends the use of the equivalent strain variation as defined by the von Mises criterion. Since the analysis is performed assuming elastic behaviour, a correction is made to determine the “real” strain using the procedure detailed in RB3261. The number of cycle to rupture N_f is then calculated starting from the total calculated strain $\Delta\varepsilon_{tot}$ by using the fatigue “design curves” specific to each material and given in Annex A3 of the code as show in Figure 13. Fatigue *design* curves are derived from continuous cycling failure tests under imposed uniaxial strain by shifting average experimental curves (“*best fit*” curves) by a factor corresponding to the most severe of the following cases (Figure 13):

- division of the strain variation by a factor of 2,
- division of the number of cycles by a factor of 20.

These factors are intended to cover effects such as environmental effects, surface state, scale effects (between the material and the test piece) and dispersion of the results (due for example to the variability of material characteristics).

Figure 13: Construction of the fatigue design curve in RCC-MRx

The analysis for welded joints implies deducing the fatigue curve for the welded joint from the fatigue curve for the base metal using a characteristic coefficient J_f , referred as the “fatigue joint coefficient”. The coefficient J_f expresses the amplification that has to be applied to the strain variation occurring in a homogeneous structural component (without weld) to obtain the strain amplitude determining the number of cycles to failure N_r of the welded component as shown in Figure 14. For each value of the number of cycles N_r , the fatigue joint coefficient $J_f (\geq 1)$ is obtained by dividing the ordinate of the design fatigue curve for the base metal by the ordinate of the design fatigue curve for the welded joint.

Figure 14: Joint coefficient J_f for calculation of the number of cycles to failure in fatigue

Fatigue tests have been performed on specimens sampled from a narrow-TIG welded plate joint procured by CEA. The base metal consists of 30 mm thick grade Z10CDVNB9-1 plates procured from FRAMATOME-ANP and the filler metal is the KOBE TGS-9CB wire (pour No. EZ00773) made by KOBE STEEL. Chemical compositions are given in Table 10 and Table 11. The weldments have been made by FRAMATOME-ANP. A relaxation heat treatment at 740°C for 10 hours 30 minutes was applied to the joint after production.

Additional fatigue tests on homogeneous specimens with only base or weld metal were also performed by the CEA to characterize their mechanical behaviour in view of FE simulations. All tests were performed in strain control and a loading ratio R equal to 1 and for a temperature of 550°C.

C	Mn	P	S	Si	Cu	Ni	Cr	Mo	Al	
0.086	0.363	0.017	0.0010	0.324	0.068	0.149	8.910	0.917	0.018	
Nb	V	N₂	Sn	Zr	Ti	As	W	B	Sb	O₂
0.08	0.198	0.0411	0.005	0.001	0.002	0.0122	0.010	0.0010	0.0006	0.0018

Table 10: Chemical composition of the 9Cr grade 91 steel plate (% mass)

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cu	Ni	Cr	Mo	V	Nb
0.08	0.18	1.00	0.004	0.005	0.17	0.71	9.03	0.90	0.18	0.08

Table 11: Chemical composition of KOBE filler wire (% mass)

Figure 15 presents the monotonic and the cyclic behaviour of the base metal and the weld metal. Although the monotonic curves are very near, the cyclic curve of the weld metal is above the base metal's one. Indeed the softening of the base metal is larger.

Figure 16 presents the results of fatigue tests on the filler metal and welded junctions, and compares them with the best fit fatigue curve of the base metal. One can see that the weld metal and bimaterial tests are below the base metal fatigue curve. Moreover, the weld metal and bimaterial tests points appear very near although the control of the strain is based in the base metal for the bimaterial specimens. Also, in bimaterial specimens, two types of failure were observed in function of the loading level as reported in Figure 16 and shown in Figure 17: for the higher strain rate, the failure of the specimen appears in the Heat Affected Zone (HAZ), while for the lower strain rate, the failure appears in the base metal part of the specimen.

Figure 15: Monotonic and cyclic softening curves of the base metal and the weld metal at T=550°C

Figure 16: Results of fatigue tests on 9Cr filler metal and welded junction

Figure 17: Different type of failure in bimaterial specimens.

FE simulations of fatigue tests on bimaterial specimens were performed to assess if it was possible to reproduce the number of cycles leading to failure as well as the different locations of failure. All calculations have been performed with the FE code Cast3m developed in CEA [34]. Overall, considering that the location of failure is difficult to predict in the “transition zone” of intermediate strain ranges, the results of FE simulations show a good agreement with experimental results. Moreover, the different failure modes can be explained by the different mechanical behaviour of the weld and base metals. However, the number of cycles to failure is always considerably higher in FE simulations and as such they cannot be used to predict the values of the fatigue joint coefficient.

As it can be seen in Figure 16, for the lowest loads failure occurs in the base metal. For sufficiently high loads (more than $\sim 0.4\%$ strain), fatigue strength is significantly reduced in comparison with fatigue strength for the base metal, and initiation takes place mainly in the heat-affected zone. Therefore, the fatigue coefficient must be higher for “high” strain variations (more than 0.4%) than for lower variations. The difference in location (BM/HAZ) is due to the reduction in fatigue strength. Figure 16 refers however to the best fit curve of the base material. In order to determine a *design* fatigue joint coefficient it is at first necessary to determine the “best fit” curve of the welded junction and then apply the $N/2$ and $\Delta\varepsilon/20$ margins to obtain the fatigue design curve. The

two design curves can then be compared. A similar approach is used, where the margins are applied directly to the experimental points and then a formulation for the joint coefficient J_f is determined so that points representative of best-fit margins can be located relative to the design curve for the base metal. To take into account the different failure modes a relation is searched by minimising the least squares difference between points $[\log(N) , \log(\Delta\varepsilon)]$ defined on three intervals $]0,\alpha], [\alpha,\beta], [\beta,\infty[$, constant at the two ends and linear between them. Determination of $[\alpha,\beta]$ forms part of the search. The following relation is proposed:

$$J_f = 1.35 \quad \text{for} \quad 0 \leq \Delta\varepsilon \leq 0.25$$

$$J_f = 1.35 + \frac{2}{3}(\Delta\varepsilon - 0.25) \quad \text{for} \quad 0.25 \leq \Delta\varepsilon \leq 0.55$$

$$J_f = 1.55 \quad \text{for} \quad 0.55 < \Delta\varepsilon$$

The application of the proposed fatigue joint coefficients is shown in Figure 18. We can see that this definition of J_f allows positioning the bimaterial test points on the base metal curve.

Figure 18: Application of a design joint coefficient J_f "defined by intervals"

7.2 Determination of fatigue joint coefficients in 316H tube weldments in R5

The work relates to the development of the R5 procedures for assessing high temperature weldments [35]. The R5 procedures have been developed by EDF Energy to support the operation and safety of the UK Advanced Gas Cooled Reactor (AGR) nuclear power plant components. These procedures make use of Fatigue Strength Reduction Factors (FSRFs) for the assessment of the fatigue and creep-fatigue life of the boiler and pipework coolant circuit steel components operating in the high temperature creep regime. R5 Volumes 2/3, Appendix A4 covers the assessment of crack initiation in weldments. In this respect, it should be noted that R5 is a procedure for assessing the lifetime of components in operation, and is not a design code such as

RCC-MR and ASME III which include aspects such as material procurement, fabrication, welding and examination etc. necessary for design.

The foundation of the extant weldment assessment procedure in R5 Volume 2/3 is the Fatigue Strength Reduction Factor (FSRF) which is derived from tests on complete weldments. The FSRF is applied to the nominal strain range remote from the weldment in conjunction with the parent material fatigue curve in order to take into account the weld fatigue reduction effects due to the weldment local geometric discontinuity and material variation. The FSRF performs a similar function to the J_f factor in RCC-MR, although the factors are not directly comparable. Currently, there are two separate assessment routes for weldments in the undressed (or as-welded) and dressed conditions, and FSRFs are provided for three different weldment types (based on RCC-MR classifications) for best estimate and lower bound assessments as shown in Table 12 and Table 13.

R5 TYPES	RCC-MR TYPES	DRESSED $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}(P+Q+F)$	UNDRESSED $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}(P+Q)$
1	I.1, I.2, I.3, II.1	1.5	1.5
2	III.1, III.2	1.5	2.5
3	V, VI, VII	N/A	3.2

Table 12: FSRFs to be applied to mean parent fatigue data for best estimate of endurance for austenitic weldments.

R5 TYPES	RCC-MR TYPES	DRESSED $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}(P+Q+F)$	UNDRESSED $\Delta\bar{\epsilon}(P+Q)$
1	I.1, I.2, I.3, II.1	2.0	2.0
2	III.1, III.2	2.0	3.0
3	V, VI, VII	N/A	4.0

Table 13: FSRFs to be applied to mean parent fatigue data for lower bound estimate of endurance for austenitic weldments.

For creep-fatigue assessments, creep damage is evaluated using the stress at the start of the dwell or hold period. For dressed weldments, where the geometry of the weldment is known, this can be derived from, for example, finite element analysis; however, for as-welded weldments, where the detailed surface geometry is not known, resort is made to using the FSRF as a strain concentration factor in determining the start-of-dwell stress.

In [33], a modified procedure, which should be included in the next edition of R5 is developed. The aim of the improved methodology procedure is to reduce the conservatism in the creep damage calculation in the creep-fatigue life assessments for as-welded weldments. A schematic illustrating the steps in the proposed modified procedure is reproduced in Figure 19

Figure 19 : Schematic of the Modified Assessment Procedure.

Essentially, the modified procedure follows the existing as-welded route but uses a Weld Strain Enhancement Factor (WSEF) instead of a Fatigue Strength Reduction Factor (FSRF), as used in the existing procedure. The extant FSRF is made up of two fatigue endurance reduction effects: firstly, the geometric strain enhancement effect (which is termed the WSEF in the modified procedure) due to the weldment geometry (if applicable) and the material mis-match between the constituent weldment materials; and secondly, the non-geometric fatigue endurance reduction effect due to the presence of small imperfections in the weldment material, which is termed the Weld Endurance Reduction, WER, in the modified procedure. In fatigue calculations, the combination of the WSEF and WER is generally equivalent to the FSRF (as shown in Figure 19) and should result in broadly the same fatigue endurance predictions using the modified and existing procedures. However, in the creep damage calculation, because the WSEF is smaller than the FSRF (as it does not include the WER) this will result in a lower start-of-dwell stress and, consequently, a less conservative estimate of creep damage. The WSEFs are derived from the same weldment database as the FSRFs but are determined relative to a reduced parent material fatigue endurance curve (i.e. minus the WER, as shown by the dashed line in Figure 20). The WER corresponds to the removal of the nucleation phase (i.e. N_i cycles corresponding to the formation of a defect size, $a_i=0.02\text{mm}$) from the fatigue endurance curve and is intended to represent the reduction in endurance due to small imperfections arising from the welding process. Details of the derivation of the WSEFs, are given in [33] and are reproduced in Table 15. Note that the modified procedure has a single route for both dressed and as-welded weldments.

Figure 20: Schematic of the Effect of the WSEF and WER on Base-line Fatigue Endurance.

Fatigue tests have been performed on miniature parent and cross-weld tube extract specimens, 2-pass weld extract specimens, and the thin-walled welded tubes. The results of all the tests are presented in Figure 21. FSRFs are derived relative to the parent material fatigue curve and the values derived from the thin-walled welded tube tests are provided in Table 14. Comparison with the R5 Volume 2/3 extant FSRFs in Table 12 and Table 13 shows that the FSRFs for tubular welded specimens are slightly greater than the lower bound values.

Specimen ID	T.S.R.	F.S.R.F.
	(%)	(%)
AAAU	1.5	2.65
AAAB	0.6	2.02
AAAY	0.4	2.13
AAAO	0.4	2.23
AAAC	0.3	2.40

Table 14: FSRFs derived from the thin-walled tubular weldment test results at 525°C.

R5 TYPES	RCC-MR TYPES	WSEF $\Delta\bar{\epsilon} (P+Q)$
1	I.1, I.2, I.3, II.1	1.16
2	III.1, III.2	1.23
3	V, VI, VII	1.66

Table 15: WSEFs to be applied to mean parent fatigue data best estimate of endurance for austenitic weldments

Figure 21: Comparison of fatigue endurance for the validation tests, tube extract tests, cross-weld extracts and two pass welds.

Figure 21 also shows the parent material fatigue curve minus the WER which in the proposed modified procedure is intended to take account of small imperfections in the weld material (and is represented by the removal of the nucleation phase corresponding to the formation of a defect size, $a_i=0.02\text{mm}$). The WSEFs are derived relative to the reduced parent material fatigue curve and the values for each of the tests are shown in Table 16. As with the FSRFs, the WSEFs are above the lower bound WSEF of 1.5 for a Type 1 weldment (derived by increasing the mean value of 1.16 in Table 3 by 25% which was the basis for calculating the lower bound FSRFs). Clearly, using the lower WSEF will result in less conservative creep-fatigue life predictions although the difference diminishes as the test strain range increases due to the relative smaller Q effect of the nucleation

phase compared to the crack growth phase. (Noting that a definitive WSEF value for the tubular welded specimen will need to be based on a statistically significant mean value)

Specimen ID	T.S.R.	W.S.E.F.
	(%)	(%)
AAAU	1.5	2.55
AAAB	0.6	1.78
AAAY	0.4	1.82
AAAO	0.4	1.92
AAAC	0.3	2.03

Table 16: WSEFs derived from the thin-walled tubular weldment test results at 525°C.

To demonstrate improved (i.e. less conservative) creep-fatigue life predictions, a series of validation analyses of weldment features tests have been carried out to provide back-to-back comparisons of the creep-fatigue life predictions for several weldment features tests using the R5 Volume 2/3 extant procedures using Fatigue Strength Reduction Factors (FSRFs) and the modified approach using the lesser Weld Stain Enhancement Factors (WSEF).

For the fatigue analyses, there is some variability in comparability of the endurance predictions between the two approaches, ranging from broadly similar for the Type 1 and 2 dressed weldments, to more and less conservative predictions using the modified method for the as-welded Type 1 and Type 2/3 weldments, respectively. In general, the predictions using both approaches are conservative (i.e. lower predicted cycles compared to the number of test cycles) although there are some cases where the degree of conservatism for both approaches is marginal.

For the creep-fatigue analyses, for the dressed weldments (i.e. Type 1 and Type 2), there is a general trend that the endurance predictions using the modified method are slightly more conservative (i.e. lower number of predicted cycles) compared to those of the existing route. The reason for this is that in deriving the start-of-dwell stress for dressed weldments, the modified procedure applies a WSEF derived from tests on as-welded weldments whilst the existing procedure utilises the peak stresses which are solely dependent on the lesser stress concentration effect of the weldment geometry. For the as-welded weldments (i.e. Type 1 and Type 2/3), the modified method applies a lower WSEF compared to the extant FSRF, hence the endurance predictions are less conservative (i.e. greater number of predicted cycles) with a reduced margin compared to the number of test cycles. In all cases, the endurance predictions remained conservative (i.e. lower) compared to the test cycles.

7.3 Determination of fatigue joint coefficient in 316L-N and P91 steels welded by the Hybrid Laser Welding technique

The Hybrid Laser-arc Welding process for SS316 and P91 was investigated respectively in the framework of task 6.2 and 6.3 of the MATTER project. The HLW process (Figure 22) combines the main advantages of the laser technology:

- high speed welding;
- low heat input;
- deep and narrow welds;
- low distortions;

with some advantage of the arc (GMAW for pipeline applications) source:

- good tolerance for fit-up variations;
- possibility to improve fused zone composition and microstructure by filler addition.

Figure 22: Hybrid Laser-arc Welding Process

Welded coupons of 316-L(N) and P91 were produced by CSM and ENEA using this process. Characterization of the welds (microstructure) and qualification of the basic mechanical properties (resilience, hardness, tensile strength) were performed in the respective tasks. Additional experimental fatigue tests have been performed in the framework of task 7.3 to determine the fatigue properties of the welded joints. The obtained values of the joint coefficients are presented in this section.

The results of the fatigue tests on the 316LN welded junction at 550°C are represented on Figure 23. Compared to the others specimens the rupture for the tests on two specimens 758A F and 758A H appears shorter although the causes could not be determined and a problem with the test bench cannot be excluded.

Figure 23: fatigue tests on 316LN welded junctions at 550°C

The obtained results have been compared with the best-fit curve of the base metal using data available in CEA. As a reminder, the RCC-MRx code specifies a fatigue joint coefficient equal to 1.25 for weldings of 316L-(N) steel by TIG and shielded metal arc welding. In order to assess if the same coefficient could be applied to this process, a comparison has been made by shifting the BM best-fit curve by applying the coefficients 1.20, 1.25 and 1.35, as show in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Comparison of results on 316LN welded junctions at 550°C with the best-fit curve of the base metal

Apart from the two points for which doubts on the experimental results exist, all points fall in the considered range of J_f , and even the conservative side. The obtained results seem to confirm that the fatigue life of the joint is adequate and comparable to that obtained used established and codified procedures.

For determination of fatigue joint coefficients for P91 weldments by HLW, 4 plates were tested. Welded plates SAG1 and SAG4 were subjected to post weld heat treatment at 770°C for 4h; SAG2 and SAG3 plates were heat treated at 770°C for 2h. Accordingly, 16 fatigue test specimens were made from the plates with PWHT 770°Cx4h (SAG1, SAG4 plates) and also 16 specimens were made from PWHT 770°Cx2h plates (SAG2, SAG3). Results are shown in Figure 25 and Figure 26

During the fatigue test at imposed strain values 0.4% or above, in part of the specimens seam displacement through HAZ zone was observed. It caused loss of axiality in specimens and deviation from established stress during the test cycle. In case of SAG1 and SAG4 specimens (Figure 26) the minimum strain value for seam displacement was 0.4%. For SAG2 and SAG3 specimens (Figure 25) it was higher and seam displacement occurs at 0.7% or larger strain values. In these cases fatigue crack formation in specimens was not observed. Additionally, cavities were present in weld metal of some specimens that influenced premature failure. For that reason the data from these specimens as inadequate for experimental requirements for J_f coefficient determination were not taken into account.

Figure 25: Fatigue tests of weld joints at 550°C. P91 plates SAG2 and SAG3 (PWHT 770°Cx2h)

Figure 26: Fatigue tests of weld joints at 550°C. P91 plates SAG1 and SAG4 (PWHT 770°Cx4h)

Comparing of J_f dependence on strain it is apparent that weld coefficient for PWHT 770°Cx2h J_{f2h} weldments only slightly changes. On the contrary, J_f coefficient for PWHT 770°Cx4h J_{f4h} has an obvious dependence on strain value, when increasing strain from 0.24 to 0.6% J_f values increases more than 1.6 times. Analysis of fatigue cycle characteristics shows that due to increased metal plasticity as a result of heat treatment, values of $\Delta\sigma$ decreases and component of plastic deformation $\Delta\varepsilon_p$ increases. However this change at larger $\Delta\varepsilon$ values (0.5, 0.6%) is less than at low strain values and high number of cycles. When comparing $\Delta\varepsilon_p$ values after 10000 fatigue cycles for SAG1(4h) and SAG2, SAG3 (2h) specimens at the similar values of $\Delta\sigma$ and $\Delta\varepsilon \approx 0.3\%$, value of $\Delta\varepsilon_p$ for weld SAG1 under heat treatment 770°Cx4h is 0.0260%. However it is only 0.0177% for SAG2, SAG3 (heat treatment 770°Cx2h), therefore the plastic component of the cycle is 1.5 times larger in the first case. Taking into consideration that HAZ zone is even more plastic established J_f differences between 770°Cx2h and 770°Cx4h specimens explains the increase of J_f coefficient values with decreasing strain as well as seam displacement through HAZ zone at a relatively small $\Delta\varepsilon = 0.4\%$ for 770°Cx4h specimens and at much higher $\Delta\varepsilon = 0.7\%$ for 770°Cx2h specimens. Thus, the data indicate that 4 h heat treatment duration at 770°C is too long for P91 HLW steel welds.

8 Discussion

In this section, the recommendations presented in the previous chapter are discussed with respect to the perspectives of their inclusion in the considered C&S. Possible improvements are suggested and complementary R&D activities proposed when needed.

8.1 Perspectives on ratcheting rules for P91

The work performed in task 4.2 allowed defining a new efficiency diagram specific to 9%Cr steels. This new diagram has been constructed starting from the results of tension-torsion tests performed in task 7.1 as well as other results available in literature. The experimental basis on which it relies is sound, including tests at 550°C, 450°C and 20°C. Furthermore, it has been validated for thermal ratcheting (ratcheting without primary membrane stress) thanks to the structural test performed in ENEA. The authors also propose specific limits on P_{eff} for 9%Cr steels, defined by comparison with the theoretical $2S_y$ criterion (i.e. the basis for the 3Sm rule), but taking also into account the softening behaviour. These limits are compared with those defined for austenitic steels to highlight and explain the differences. It is shown that, at 550°C these “allowable stresses” lead to very limited plastic deformation, in any case compatible with the limited ductility of P91, even when taking into account the cyclic softening behaviour. The work could however be completed by showing that ductility margins are still sufficient at different temperatures, also in comparison with austenitic steels.

Moreover, the proposed criteria do not address the effects of creep. Since in this case deformation is time-dependent, limits for the efficiency diagram rule are expressed in terms of allowable strains rather than allowable stresses, taking into account the combined effects of ratcheting and creep-deformation by means of the creep laws. More experimental tests (for example tension-torsion tests with hold times) are in this case needed.

The conclusion therefore is that, provided that the demonstration of sufficient ductility margins at different temperatures is provided, the new efficiency diagram rule could be included as proposed by the authors in the next editions of RCC-MRx for the design of P91 components in the negligible

creep domain. However, this would not cover the full operational domain of GEN-IV components, since the creep domain would not be covered. The work must therefore be completed by investigating the non-negligible creep domain by means of experimental tests with hold times and providing the same demonstration of sufficient ductility margins at different temperatures. Other types of ratcheting tests (for example internal pressure+ cyclic axial strain) could be performed, but this is not considered as mandatory.

8.2 Perspectives on creep and creep-fatigue interaction rules for P91

The first notable conclusion of the work performed in task 4.3 is that the interaction diagram for P91 as proposed today in RCC-MRx performs satisfactorily, with respect to experimental results available in literature and additional testing performed in task 7.1, at least for creep strains up to 0.5%. The main concern here was the effects of pre-cycling, which is known to decrease the creep strength of the material. This was actually verified by dedicated experimental tests, but the consequences remained limited below 0.5% creep strain, where primary creep strain rate seems largely unaffected. Still, as pointed out by the authors in their first recommendation, codes do not take this effect properly into account, since cyclic history is not taken into account in the creep damage assessment procedures. The implication of softening however is not for the creep-fatigue interaction diagram, but rather for pure creep design. In case of creep-fatigue (with relaxation) the underestimation of creep rate will cause higher creep damage factors due to higher stresses to be used for creep rupture determination. Still, improving the creep damage calculation procedure would allow decreasing the (excessive) conservatism in the codes. The problem concerns the evaluation of pure creep damage, where tests in forward creep showed a considerable increase of the creep strain rate. Appropriate factors could be introduced to correct the creep strain laws. One suggestion by the authors is to introduce a “damage parameters” that could be defined as the ratio between the peak stress of the Nth cycle and the peak stress of the first cycle. Alternative strain models, such as LCSP model could also be used.

The second recommendation concerns the use of more “phenomenological” models, which nonetheless remain manageable in terms of fitting parameters and identification procedures. The proposed models actually show very good agreement with the experimental results. While the advantages of this methodology is to avoid questions on how to choose the “representative” cycle for creep damage calculations and implicitly take into account the softening/hardening behaviour, this recommendations shall be considered in light of the several decades of experience with the creep-fatigue interaction diagram in the nuclear industry. While it is of course possible to propose inclusion of this methodology in the probationary rules section, this should be at least supported by a more exhaustive analysis and comparison with results given by the interaction diagram for others types of steel. The identification of the models should be better clarified in order to show that it always possible to obtain conservative estimations from the fitting parameters. As it stands, the option to improve creep damage calculation in the interaction diagram method seems the preferable route.

Finally, the third recommendation shall seriously be considered because it highlights a problem that is shared by all creep-damage assessment methodologies, which is the lack of experimental data in the regime of low stresses and long hold times. This regime is the relevant one for

components in nuclear reactors. Because of time constraints, creep-fatigue laboratory tests are usually performed in regime of high strain ranges and short hold times, where fatigue damage is predominant and the «creep» damage is essentially excessive strain not cavitation and intergranular damage. These types of tests, because of their duration, are difficult to perform in the limited time of a project such as MATTER but should nonetheless be carried out to validate the proposed design rules for creep and creep-fatigue damage.

8.3 Perspectives on negligible creep domain definition for P91 components.

As clearly explained in [19], the definition of the negligible creep domain for a given material is dependent of the choices of i) the reference stress for evaluating creep strain and ii) the limitation of the allowed creep strain. The reference stress to evaluate creep strain for P91 has been chosen by the authors at $0.56R_m$. The reasons for this choice, which is different from the reference stress for SS316 in RCC-MRx ($\sim 0.3R_m$) is the different ratio R_m/R_p (~ 0.8 for P91 and ~ 0.3 for SS316). This choice appears justified for P91 as explained by the authors.

The choice of the maximum allowed creep strain is instead more delicate. On one hand it is said that choosing the same limit as for austenitic steels (0.01%-0.03%) will lead to insignificant creep domain definition and on the other hand that available data only allow reliable evaluation of creep strains around the reference stress starting from $\sim 0.2\%$. It is true that it is extremely difficult to measure very small creep strains in the range of stress and temperatures relevant for the definition of NEC. In fact, definition of NEC for SS316 relies rather on relaxation data.

The authors show however that, under the assumed hypotheses, the proposed NEC curve insures very high safety margins with respect to rupture at the reference stress (>1000) and the allowable stress at temperature (>100000). This justification could be complemented by performing the same reasoning for different materials (for example SS316) and comparing the respective results. From a more general point of view, it should be justified that a (creep) strain of 0.2% does not jeopardize safety margins defined by other design rules and is more generally compatible with the ductility margins of the material. Increased creep strain rates because of cyclic softening should however not be a concern at these low strain levels as discussed in §8.2.

In conclusion, the proposed definition of the negligible creep domain for P91 is sound and could be considered for inclusion in the next edition of RCC-MRx, but additional justifications should be provided to support the choices made by the authors.

8.4 Perspectives on additional design factors

As presented in §6, besides the effects of corrosion, the main additional degradation factors for components in GEN-IV reactors are due to thermal ageing at high temperatures and irradiation damage.

As explained in [3], thermal ageing is due to the microstructural evolution of the material (base metal and weldments) at high temperatures. Chemical composition and manufacturing route are in this case the significant factors. As such, prevention of this mode of degradation is to be dealt with at the manufacturer/material specifications level. Considerable R&D has been carried out in the past to optimize, for example the chemical composition of 316LN as specified in RCC-MRx. This

route could be pursued by manufacturing small batches with different compositions for tests at laboratory level, but the effects of scale (size and shape of real components) cannot be discounted *à-priori*. The expertise on material coming from the dismantling of Phenix is a real opportunity that should be looked into. On the other hand, RCC-MRx includes a thermal ageing coefficient that reduces allowable stresses for aged materials. The problem in this case is the availability of experimental results for the evaluation of this coefficient. If a justification of 60 years lifetime is needed, the usual consensus is that an extrapolation factor of 3 on time can be accepted, which leads to testing times of ~20 years. To shorten testing times, increasing the test temperature to accelerate aging is an option but this increase is limited because of the appearance of additional degradation mechanisms. This leads to testing times of ~16 years. These kinds of tests were not achievable in the limited timeframe of the MATTER project.

For this reason, activities have mainly focused on proposing suitable extrapolation techniques starting from available results. While proposed methodologies appear justified, they have in any case to be validated by experimental results. It is assumed that the test matrix could be simplified by the use of these techniques. Still, if extrapolation is performed, it is advised to perform it before introduction of corresponding data in the codes, i.e. to not leave it to the «user».

Concerning the effects of irradiation damage, no explicit propositions are made. Curves for negligible and maximum allowed irradiation are given in RCC-MRx for 316LN, and the code includes specific rules to take into account effects of irradiation between the two domains. For example, the creep usage factor is reduced by factor of ten (0.1 instead of 1), which is more conservative than the reduction factor of 3 cited in §6.2. However, no data for irradiated conditions are given in RCC-MRx for 9%Cr steel. There is also a margin to reassess the irradiation curves given in the code with respect to the different He production/dpa ratio as a function of the energy distribution of the neutron flux.

8.5 Perspectives on welding coefficients

One of the objectives of the MATTER project was to provide a first assessment of fatigue and creep joint coefficients for P91 weldments. In fact, joint creep coefficient were added to RCC-MRx during the course of the project and the scope was redefined to investigate only fatigue joint coefficients. With respect to P91 weldments working in the non-negligible creep domain, the main issue is type-IV cracking in HAZ. A PWHT is necessary to soften the martensite formed during the weld metal solidification and to induce sufficient ductility in HAZ without excessive softening of the base metal.

Experimental fatigue tests performed in task 7.3 on narrow-TIG welded junctions at 550°C showed a reduction of the fatigue life of the specimen for high strain range variations. As a matter of fact, this reduction of fatigue life could be attributed to crack formation in the HAZ. Although the mechanical behaviour of the HAZ was not included, FE simulation allowed explaining this phenomenon as linked to the different cyclic behaviours of the base and welding metal. A fatigue joint coefficient is then proposed whose value is comprised between 1.35 (at low strain ranges and high number of cycles) and 1.55 (at high strain ranges and low number of cycles). Note that the fatigue joint coefficient included in RCC-MRx for 316SS is instead 1.25, regardless of temperature and strain range. Higher values of the joint coefficient imply higher reduction of fatigue life for the weldment with respect to the base material.

The proposed values of the fatigue joint coefficient for P91 weldments have been obtained following the methodology recommended in RCC-MRx and as such could be proposed for inclusion in the next edition of the code. Still, they are limited to 550°C and do not cover the whole range of operating temperatures of GEN-IV components. Because of the particular failure mode, the obtained results cannot be generalized to other temperatures. Actually, fatigue tests of P91 weldment were also performed at 450°C at the end of the MATTER project and showed the same type of difference in the location of failure. The joint coefficient however could not be determined since no fatigue curve for the base metal is provided at 450°C and lack of time to perform additional fatigue tests on the base metal. This activity therefore should be completed by more experimental testing at 450°C and other temperatures to confirm the obtained results.

Another objective was the development of the R5 procedures for assessing high temperature 316H weldments in UK Advanced Gas Cooled Reactor (AGR) nuclear power plant components. These procedures make use of Fatigue Strength Reduction Factors (FSRFs) for the assessment of the fatigue and creep-fatigue life of the boiler and pipework coolant circuit steel components operating in the high temperature creep regime. The improved procedure is based on separating the previous FRSF in two separate coefficients, the WER which is intended to take account of small imperfections in the weld material, and the WSEF which takes into account weldment geometry and the material mis-match between the constituent weldment materials. Due to the prolongation of the work in developing the tubular weldment specimen, it has not been possible to report on further fatigue and creep-fatigue tests on the tubular weldment specimens within the timeframe of the MATTER project. Nevertheless, this work will continue under the auspices of the R5 Development Programme proceeding beyond the end of 2014. The intention is to carry out further fatigue tests on cross-weld specimens and dressed tubular weldment specimens in order to provide a gradation of increasing fatigue reduction effects from the parent and weld metals building up to a greater understanding fatigue degradation effects in the as-welded tubular specimens. Further tests on the tubular weldment specimens under creep fatigue conditions will also be performed. To supplement these validation tests, further analyses of features tests demonstrating the conservativeness of the R5 Volume 2/3 current and proposed modified procedure for assessing the fatigue and creep-fatigue lives of weldments are provided in [33].

Finally, the fatigue endurance of the 316LN and P91 junctions manufactured with the HLW technique developed in the MATTER project was investigated. This activity was not meant to produce recommendations to be included in the codes, but rather assess the maturity of the proposed technique. Some of the produced weldments however showed defects in terms of lack of fusion and diffused porosity that prevented or jeopardized experimental testing. However, the result obtained on the sound joints showed encouraging results, especially for 316 weldments. The recommendation is therefore to promote new studies on the application of HLW.

9 Conclusions

This report constitutes the deliverable D4.8 – «Synthesis of the recommendations» of the Work Package 4 - «Design Rules» of the MATTER project. It presents a synthesis of the outcomes of the activities performed in Domain 2 – «Prenormative R&D for Codes and Standards» with the

objective to revise and update the design rules in order to answer to some short term needs of the two projects ASTRID & MYRRHA with respect to the design and the construction of the structural components.

Several tasks within the Domain 2 of the MATTER project were devoted to the improvement of selected design rules contained in present-day C&S for which uncertainties existed with respect to GEN-IV reactor materials and operating conditions. The recommendations issued by these tasks have been summarized and presented in the respective chapters of this report. They are further discussed in view of their possible inclusion in the selected C&S. Suggestions on how to improve them are given when necessary.

Overall, the work performed in DM2 has allowed considerable progress in the understanding and modelling of relevant damage phenomena in selected materials for Gen-IV reactors. Most of the work was devoted to the design rules for P91 9%Cr steel, a material characterized by a reduced ductility and a cyclic softening behaviour. In this respect, ratcheting, fatigue and creep fatigue interaction were the main identified issues for which improvements of design rules or new assessment methodologies were proposed.

The outcomes of these activities have paved the way for further development of present-day C&S, the main reserve being the necessity to perform additional experimental tests, either to support the justification of the proposed rules or to extend their domain of validity. The principal issue in this case is the long duration of experimental tests like those required for creep or thermal ageing which could not be performed in the limited timeframe of the MATTER and for which very few data exist in (open) literature.

References

- [1] European Sustainable Nuclear Industrial Initiative website : <http://www.snetp.eu/>
- [2] RCC-MRx, «Règles de Conception et de construction des matériels Mécaniques des installations nucléaires» (Design and construction rules for Mechanical equipment in nuclear facilities), published by AFCEN, 2012 edition.
- [3] M. Blat-Yreix, S. Dubiez-Le Goff, MATTER- Deliverable D5.4, Additional design data proposition and justification.
- [4] C. Schroer (KIT), S. Holmström (JRC), K-F Nilsson (JRC), MATTER Deliverable D5.5 – Recommendation for additional design factors.
- [5] O. Ancelet et al, MATTER deliverable D4.3, Review of the existing rules for ratcheting.
- [6] G. Clément, J. Lebey, R. Roche. A design rule for thermal ratcheting, 5th International Conference on Pressure Vessel Technology - Vol. 1- Design and Analysis - San Francisco ,1984.
- [7] G. Aiello, P. Matheron, K. Zhang, J. Aktaa, M. E. Angiolini, G. M. Giannuzzi, D. Mele, L. Pilloni, L. Sipione, MATTER deliverable D4.4 - Recommendation for ratcheting rules for P91 components.
- [8] D. Bernardi et al, MATTER deliverable D7.1 – Synthesis of experimental work for design rules improvement.
- [9] P. Matheron, G. Aiello, C. Caes, P. Lamagnere, A. Martin, M. Sauzay, Tension–torsion ratcheting tests on 9Cr steel at high temperature, Nuclear Engineering and Design, Volume 284, 1 April 2015, Pages 207-214, ISSN 0029-5493
- [10] R. Pohja, S. Holmström, K. Nilsson, W. Payten, H.-Y. Lee and J. Aktaa, MATTER – Deliverable D4.5, Creep-fatigue interaction rules for P91.
- [11] Rami Pohja, Stefan Holmström, Hyeong-Yeon Lee, MATTER – Deliverable D4.6, Recommendation for Creep and Creep-fatigue assessment for P91 Components.
- [12] S. Manson, "A simple procedure for estimating high-temperature low cycle fatigue," *Experimental Mechanics*, vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 349-355, 1968.
- [13] S. Manson and G. Halford, "A method of estimating high temperature low cycle fatigue behaviour of materials," NASA Technical Memorandum - NASA TM X -52270, 1967
- [14] T. Asayama, Y. Tachibana, "Collect Available Creep-Fatigue Data and Study Existing Creep-Fatigue Evaluation Procedures for Grade 91 and Hastelloy XR, DOE/ASME Generation IV Materials Project, A report on Task 5 submitted to ASME ST-LLC, Revision 3 Final Report," JAEA, 2007.
- [15] S. Holmström and P. Auerkari, "A robust model for creep-fatigue life assessment," *Materials Science and Engineering A*, vol. 559, no. 1, pp. 333-335, 2013.
- [16] R. Pohja et al., "A study of creep-fatigue interaction in the nickel-base superalloy 263," in 10th Liege Conference on Materials for Advanced Power Engineering, 2014.
- [17] B. Wilshire, P. Scharming and R. Hurst, "A new approach to creep data assessment," *Material Science and Engineering A*, Vols. 510-511, pp. 3-6, 2009.
- [18] "NIMS creep data sheet. Atlas of creep deformation property No. D-1. Creep deformation properties of 9Cr-1Mo-V-Nb steel tubes for boiler and heat exchanger," NIMS, 2007.
- [19] Stefan Holmström, Chen Jia-Chao, MATTER - Deliverable 5.3, Recommendation for the negligible creep domain for P91.
- [20] B. Riou et. Al, Proc. of ASME Pressure Vessels and Piping Division Conference, PVP2006- ICPVT-11, paper: 93408. Canada, 2006
- [21] W. Ren, T. Lillo, T. Totemeier, Assessment of Negligible Creep, Off-Normal Welding and heat treatment of Gr91 Steel for nuclear reactor pressure vessel application, ORNL/GEN4/LTR-06-032, 2006.
- [22] B. Riou, Improvement of ASME NH for Grade 91 Negligible Creep and Creep Fatigue STP-NU-13, 2008
-

- [23] T. ASAYAMA and T. KAITO : “Development of Structural Materials for JSFR – Overview and Current Status”, FR13 meeting, International Conference on Fast Reactor and related Fuel Cycles, Safe technologies and Sustainable scenarios, Paris, 4-7 mars 2013
- [24] S. Dubiez-Le Goff and al.: “Qualification of the materials of ASTRID for 60 years lifetime”, International Conference on Fast Reactors and Related Fuel Cycles: Safe Technologies and Sustainable Scenarios (FR13) – 4-7 March 2013, Paris
- [25] R. Swindeman, M. Santella, P. Maziasz, B. Roberts, K. Coleman, Issues in replacing Cr–Mo steels and stainless steels with 9Cr–1Mo–V steel, International Journal of Pressure Vessels and Piping 81 (2004) 507–512.
- [26] Preliminary Materials Selection Issues for the Next generation Nuclear Plant Reactor Pressure Vessel, Argonne Nuclear Engineering Division, ANL/EXT-06/45, http://nuclear.inl.gov/deliverables/docs/anl-ext-06-45_report.pdf
- [27] B. Dyson, Use of CDM in Materials Modeling and Component Creep Life Prediction, Journal of Pressure vessel Technology, Vol. 122, 2000, 281-296
- [28] R.L. Klueh, D.R. Harries, Irradiation damage, irradiation facilities, irradiation testing, in: High- Chromium Ferritic and Martensitic Steels for Nuclear Application, American Society for Testing Materials, West Conshocken, PA., 2001, pp. 81–89.
- [29] R.L. Klueh, D.R. Harries, Elevated-temperature helium embrittlement, in: High-Chromium Ferritic and Martensitic Steels for Nuclear Application, American Society for Testing Materials, West Conshocken, PA., 2001, pp. 135–138.
- [30] K. Tuček, K.-F. Nilsson, P. Baeten, D. Tice, Design Rules for Heavy Liquid Metal Cooled Fast Reactors, 2014, Materials Testing and Rules (MATTER), 7th EURATOM Framework Programme, Grant Agreement no. 269706, Deliverable D9.3.
- [31] T. Asayama, Y. Abe, N. Miyaji, M. Koi, T. Furukawa, E. Yoshida, Evaluation procedures for irradiation effects and sodium environmental effects for the structural design of Japanese fast breeder reactors, Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology 123 (2001) 49–57.
- [32] G. Aiello, J. Aktaa, F. Cismondi, G. Rampal, J.-F. Salavy, F. Tavassoli, Assessment of design limits and criteria requirements for Eurofer structures in TBM components, Journal of Nuclear Materials 414 (2011) 53–68.
- [33] G. Aiello, P. Matheron, O. Ancelet, L. Forest, G. Smith, G. Dundulis, A. Grybėnas, MATTER deliverable D6.1 - Recommendation for the weld coefficients.
- [34] <http://www-cast3m.cea.fr>
- [35] R5 Assessment Procedure for the High Temperature Response of Structures, Issue 3, Rev 001, EDF Energy, 2012.